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Research Article

**BRAIN-HEART INTERACTION: CARDIAC
COMPLICATIONS AFTER STROKE**¹Dr Hafiz Muhammad Umair, ²Dr Hina Habib, ³Dr Samra Hassan.¹MBBS, Islamabad Medical and Dental College, Islamabad.^{2,3}MBBS, Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur.**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Neurocardiology is an emerging and interesting discipline that addresses the brain and heart interactions, like effects of brain injury on heart functioning or effects of cardiac injury on the brain. This review paper encapsulates cardiac dysfunctions owing to strokes like ischemic stroke, brain hemorrhagic stroke and subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH). The high mortality rate in heart or brain injuries is mostly due to neurological damage and cardiovascular complications, where the latter is the second leading cause of death after stroke. Experimental and clinical evidence showed a prominent relationship between heart dysfunction and brain damage.

Thus, it is mandatory to determine whether a stroke triggers cardiac dysfunction or it is owing to some underlying causes of stroke. Stroke induced cardiac dysfunction can lead to life long cardiac problems, fatality, or mild recoverable damage like Takotsubo cardiomyopathy and neurogenic stress cardiomyopathy (NSC). Different underlying mechanisms in brain- heart interactions are discussed in this paper.

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INTRODUCTION:

In patients with cerebrovascular disease, cardiac injury is common. ^{1,2} In 1947, it was first found by Byer and colleagues that myocardial damage and arrhythmia can be caused by cerebral vascular disease. ⁴ The speciality that deals with brain-heart interaction is now called as neurocardiology. ⁵ Basically, stroke like hemorrhagic, ischemic or SAH, can disrupt cerebral auto-regulation and induce neurovascular uncoupling, which directly impacts the cerebral blood flow depending upon the cardiac function. ⁶

Numerous interactions occur based upon different CVD and cerebrovascular diseases. In acute stroke patients, even if the primary heart disease is absent still myocardial injury, ischemia like electrocardiographic changes and arrhythmias are frequently observed which support CNS, an origin of these abnormal ECG. ^{1-3,7}

On the basis of evidence based study, it is likely that there exist some relationship between brain and heart injuries and their impacts upon each other. It is, therefore, imperative to sort out and understand this relationship to help the patients in improving their recovery life and reducing mortality rate and organ dysfunction.

Stroke and Cardiac Damage: Risk Factors and Preexisting Heart Disease

Complications that immediately lead to morbidity and mortality after cardiac damage owing to acute stroke include heart attack, cardiac arrest, congestive heart failure, abnormal heart rhythms and blood pressure issues. Converging issues like hypertension, diabetes, age, and high cholesterol level, all are factors for cerebrovascular or cardiovascular diseases and exacerbate cardiac injury independent of stroke causes. Therefore, it is found that severe heart problems might be owing to systemic dysfunction triggered by inflammation, immune response and vascular damage as in hypertension and diabetes, where in spite of direct neural causation, brain can act to worsen heart functioning. A Framingham study has revealed that the chances of stroke occurrence can double up in the presence of coronary heart disease, triple up in hypertension, presence, and rises four fold with cardiac failure and atrial fibrillation. ^{8,9}

Cardiac diseases cause about 20% of ischemic strokes. Moreover, atrial fibrillation, on one hand, is common tachyarrhythmia in acute stroke, and on the other hand it is also linked with higher risk of systemic thromboembolism. People with increasing age are greatly affected by heart failure owing to functional or structural damage to the heart induced by ventricular blood filling or ejection fraction.

Cardiac Damage Owing to Stroke

After a stroke, the 2nd major cause of death worldwide is CVD complications. Stroke can induce cardiac damage and it can lead to fatality, lifelong problems, or recoverable mild damages like NSC and Takotsubo cardiomyopathy. When left ventricular ejection fraction is reduced, then NSC is diagnosable, along with ventricular wall motion abnormalities and increased cardiac serum enzymes. On the other hand, Takotsubo cardiomyopathy is caused by psychological stress in the absence of physical brain damage and has symptoms similar to NSC. The telltale sign of Takotsubo cardiomyopathy is weakening of heart muscle cells which causes ballooning.

• Cardiac Damage Induced by Hemorrhagic Stroke

Clinical data and experimental studies have shown that 40 to 100% abnormalities in ECG are found in SAH patients and 5% of these SAH patients have severe cardiac arrhythmias. After SAH, prolonged hospital delay and increased risk of cardiovascular comorbidity are associated with cardiac arrhythmias. Elevated levels of creatine phosphokinase-myocardial fraction mass (CKMB) and Troponin T levels in left side of hemorrhagic intracerebral stroke patients are also associated with life threatening ventricular arrhythmia. 80% of patients shows abnormal ECG changes within 1 year of hemorrhagic stroke.

It is found that, less severe ECG changes lead to structural alteration as QTc, but cannot predict ventricular wall abnormalities, and severe ECG changes like an inverted T or increased Troponin levels released by damaged myocytes can predict abnormalities in ventricular wall motion. Acute cardiac dysfunction is independently linked with hospital death and directly linked with declined 1 year outcome of functions. LVDD depicts anomalies in the atrial filling by atrial contraction, venous return, and ventricular relaxation abilities. LVDD is a result of cardio-embolic stroke and more than 50% of the SAH patients develop it (LVDD), despite their suffering from origin that is non-cardioembolic.

• Cardiac Damage Induced by Ischemic Stroke

Cardiac complications rises proportionally with the severity of the neurological deficits and ischemic stroke. Similarly, when the heart is affected by severe ischemic stroke, then it becomes a predictor of future secondary severe complications. In a clinical trial based study, it is found that during the 3 months of acute ischemic stroke, about 19% of patients faces one of the severe cardiac complications; 28% develop LVEF and less than 50% develop systolic dysfunction. Approximately

67% of patients with acute systemic stroke, ECG abnormalities within 24 hours is common and one of the common cause of death is cardiac arrhythmias. Around 88% of patients who go through the insular cortex in the right cerebral hemisphere and survives it, develop myocardial injury within weeks of stroke.

However, secondary complications like pulmonary edema, vasospasm, and delayed cerebral ischemia

need active management. Evidence has revealed that cardiac dysfunction can be caused by ischemic stroke even if the risk factors of pre-existing heart disease are absent. During the starting 3 months after ischemic stroke about 19% of patients suffer from one of serious cardiac adverse events; 29% develops LVEF; and 13 to 30% faces systolic dysfunction.^{10, 11}

Mechanism of Brain-Heart Interaction After Stroke

1. Hypothalamic-Pituitary Adrenal Axis (HPA), Catecholamine Surge and Sympathetic Parasympathetic Regulation After Stroke

Depression develops in many patients owing to their functional deficit. Post stroke depression, anxiety, fear, stress and other psychological aspects are biochemical in nature and greatly depends upon the functional deficits of brain. Ischemic stroke triggers Takotsubo cardiomyopathy. The master regulatory blood hormone which integrates stress, emotions, metabolism and physical activities is HPA axis. 3 endocrine glands are present in HPA axis: pituitary, hypothalamus and adrenal glands, very important for neuroendocrine system. Under stress ACTH is released which in turn stimulates the adrenal glands to release cortisol hormone. The latter is linked with stroke severity and level of insulin damage. Prolonged levels of cortisol hormone is neurotoxic and rises mortality rate. Rostral ventrolateral medulla is directly projected by paraventricular nucleus, which integrates

cardiac afferents, baroreceptor, and inputs from upper brain regions to the heart sympathetic outflow. ECG abnormalities, myocardial necrosis and arrhythmias are induced by sympathetic output after the hypothalamus activation.

The catecholamine is closely associated with heart damage and physical emotional stressors. Catecholamine can cause myocardial ischemia or cardiac hypertrophy. Adrenal glands release catecholamine and brain injury elevates its secretory level. Neurologic injury leads to excessive circulation and release of its from myocardial nerve endings due to damage in nerve adjacent to myocardial nerve. Long term release and circulation of catecholamine can cause cardio toxicity and can trigger edema in regions of transient fibrosis, hypokinesia, inflammation and

contraction band necrosis. β receptors are worked upon by catecholamine that increases the strength and rate of contraction of the heart. These receptors combine with G protein and increases cystolic cAMP. The latter binds to protein kinase A which indirectly overloads mitochondria by regulating different L-type Ca^{2+} channels. This causes the death of myocardial cells. Pre-treatment of beta blockers has shown the decline in the incidence of this cell death and myocardial lesions.

Forebrain plays an important role in autonomic nervous system regulation in patients with stroke. Frontal lobe and anterior regulate gyrus affects heart rate and blood pressure. Ischemic lesion in the insular cortex can increase cardiac complications' risk and cause cardiac arrhythmias, blood pressure issues and myocytolysis. Location of ischemic lesion negatively impacts heart functions. It is evident that right insular lesions decline sympathetic tone and causes over activity in parasympathetic activity. Elevated activity of either of the hemisphere can increase the adverse cardiac outcomes, long term mortality and decreased cardiac wall motion. Therefore, intensive heart check and monitoring is imperative for patients who had stroke.^{12, 13}

2. Blood Brain Barrier Disruption

The NVU is a functional unit of brain which encompass metabolic interactions between neuronal, glial and vascular components. THE blood brain barrier (BBB) is at the core of NVU and composed of endothelial cells, astrocytic end feet, pericytes and thick basement membrane. The BBB limits the entry of potential neurotoxins and microscopic and hydrophilic molecules in the brain from circulatory system. BBB also protects the brain from variations in blood composition and maintain a neutral environment. The disruption in the NUV and BBB is disastrous and can cause pathophysiological cascade after stroke and tissue damage. Inflammatory factors are promoted.

Cardiac surgery and dysfunction can cause cerebral ischmeia and stroke via hypoperfusion and embolization of heart. BBB disruption causes the entry of antigens in the brain and extracellular vesicles enter the blood stream from the brain. Therefore, there exist a correlation between BBB and brain-heart interaction.^{14, 15}

3. Immuno-response and Systemic Inflammation

The immune system is activated owing to inflammation after stroke. This activation is a major risk progression. Local and systemic inflammation responses after stroke includes circulating signals, immune cell types and is imperative for secondary complications and infections.

Brain receives local inflammation responses, endothelial cell damage triggers signals and increases oxidative stress which lead to BBB disruption after stroke. Damaged endothelial cells and astrocytes stimulate the release of proinflammatory cytokine and chemokines, activates resident microglia and macrophages (infiltrating) that assume M1 phenotype as well as the spleen itself. Therefore, systemic inflammatory responses are triggered by number of stress hormones, cytokines, chemokines and sympathetic and parasympathetic regulation.

After a stroke, gut microbiome dysbiosis which can cause endotoxin or bacterial translocation to the blood which ultimately causes systemic inflammation. DAMPs which are released by the dying brain cells after ischemic stroke releases antigen, which can go through the BBB and become part of the systemic circulation. Upon reaching peripheral organs like liver, the microRNA and protein cargo of dying endothelial cells regulate cytokine response and mediate peripheral immune cell trafficking to injured brain tissue.¹⁶

The coupling of parasympathetic dysfunction with catecholamine release triggers inflammation that can induce thrombi formation, myocardial dysfunction and cardiomyocyte cell death. Thus, inflammation plays significant role in brain injury and cardiac damage after stroke. ¹⁷

CONCLUSION:

The brain-heart syndrome (interaction) after stroke is prominent and impacts the prognosis, morbidity and mortality of patients. Secondary brain damage due to heart dysfunction and impaired systemic & brain homeostasis is a serious issue. Although, there is a requirement of proper management to prevent secondary cardiac complications after a stroke, there is a dearth of data to provide guidance over this matter. Clinical trials have shown that diagnosis of brain-heart disease at an early stage can reduce mortality and enable proper management.

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